

CURRENT ISSUES OF TEACHING UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Аннотация. В данной статье представлены актуальные вопросы преподавания узбекского и русского языков в условиях глобализации, основные цели и задачи обучения узбекскому и русскому языкам, знания и подготовка к работе.

Annotation. This article presents the current issues of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages in the process of globalization, the main goals and tasks of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages, knowledge and preparation for work.

Ключевые слова. Процесс глобализации, узбекский язык, русский язык, знание языков, переводческая способность, межкультурализм.

Keywords. Globalization process, Uzbek language, Russian language, language knowledge, translation ability, interculturalism.

The process of globalization is a concept that represents the interdependence and integration of the world's economic, political, social and cultural environments instead of interdependence and integration. The main reason for this process is the increasing interconnection of communication, transport, technologies and financial changes, strengthening the interaction of countries in the world, efforts aimed at regulating issues such as trade, investments, tariffs and migration. The process of globalization includes various spheres, for example, economic, political, cultural, social laws. During this process, international trade, services and financing environments will expand. Foreign loans to large companies and foreign investments, access to new markets, interaction, transnational corporations and global organizations are expanding.

If we look at the current issues of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages in the process of globalization, it is unique. Below are some relevant issues:

- it is important to have enough uniform resources and teaching materials for teaching Uzbek and Russian languages. Finding and making available curricula, textbooks, grammar books, dictionaries and other teaching materials designed for these languages can be challenging.

- Finding sufficient teachers to teach Uzbek and Russian languages is also an important issue. It is necessary to develop advanced educational institutions to train specialist teachers, translators and engineers in the field of Uzbek and Russian philology. Sufficient personnel is also important for the education of pupils and students.

- distribution and teaching methods are also important in teaching Uzbek and Russian languages. It will be useful to use applications and technologies, conduct interactive lessons, communicate with students through online platforms and mobile applications, and create opportunities to put the Uzbek and Russian languages into practice.

- in the process of globalization, the development of the Uzbek and Russian languages and the appearance of new words, expressions and concepts are normal. Here, students should be taught to learn, use and translate new words and expressions.

- the announcement of fields related to the Uzbek and Russian languages and their requirements are also relevant. Translators are needed in diplomatic fields, leading specialists in business languages, and researchers in Uzbek and Russian languages are needed in academic fields.

These are the current issues of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages in the process of globalization. These issues and other problems are the primary problem in teaching and using Uzbek and Russian languages. In order to learn in this process, it is important to work patiently and efficiently, and to adopt new methods.

The main tasks of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages are to increase students' motivation, to implement their mastered studies, to make the learning process interesting, to increase attention to news. The main goals and tasks of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages are as follows:

- the main goal of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages is to increase students' familiarity with grammar, vocabulary, phonetics and pragmatics in these languages. This includes developing their understanding of the rules and structure of language, and improving their speaking, writing and reading skills.

- the main goal of language learning is to develop students' communication skills in Uzbek and Russian languages. This includes preparing them to express themselves, ask questions, answer questions, and talk about a variety of topics.

- the goal of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages is to develop the ability of students to translate texts from Uzbek or Russian into languages other than Uzbek or Russian and to develop high-quality interpretation skills. This helps them to understand and translate existing texts, as well as understand which languages to collaborate in the culture of translation.

- in the process of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages, students are encouraged to approach the main works of Uzbek and Russian literature, writers, creators, and the general history of their culture. It helps them to understand the important part of literary heritage and culture, to develop their understanding of literary genres, writers, teachers and their works.

- the goal of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages is to make students acquire basic knowledge of Uzbek and Russian languages. This will help them to understand more comprehensive topics of Uzbek and Russian literature, historical events, national and social environments.

-an additional goal of teaching Uzbek and Russian languages is to develop students as bilingual and intercultural individuals. This includes preparing them to communicate on any topic between different countries and societies, to develop their knowledge of Uzbek and Russian languages, to develop interdependence and mutual relations.

Based on the teaching of Uzbek and Russian languages, it is desirable to prepare students for contact with other fields of science and to prepare them for future work. This will help them learn to write scientific papers, participate in conferences, put their language skills into practice, and learn to collaborate in other areas.

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